

PREDICTION OF MORTALITY AND MORBIDITY IN PATIENTS WITH SECONDARY PERITONITIS USING POMPP VERSUS PULP SCORING SYSTEM

Ansar Raza Mohsin^{*1}, Prof. Dr Khalid Masood Gondal², Noor-ul-Ain Mujahid³,
Dr Muhammad Imran⁴, Muhammad Talha Khan⁵, Ali Raza⁶

^{*1,4,5}Postgraduate Resident Surgery, Mayo Hospital, Lahore

²Vice Chancellor Fatima Jinnah Medical University (FJMU), Lahore

³Assistant Professor General Surgery, Mayo Hospital, Lahore

⁶Postgraduate Resident Medicine, Mayo Hospital, Lahore

ansarmalik7766@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *
Ansar Raza Mohsin

Abstract

Background: Secondary peritonitis is a common surgical emergency in low- and middle-income countries, with mortality rates ranging from 15% to 30%. **Objective:** To compare the predictive accuracy of the Peritonitis Mortality Prediction (POMPP) score and the Peptic Ulcer Perforation (PULP) score in patients with secondary peritonitis. **Methods:** This cross-sectional validation study was conducted at the North Surgical Ward, Department of Surgery, Mayo Hospital, Lahore, from 25 January 2025 to 5 June 2025, included 159 patients aged 18–75 years presenting with secondary peritonitis. POMPP and PULP scores were calculated for each patient. Patients were followed until discharge or death, and mortality outcomes were recorded. **Results:** The mean age of patients was 44.7 ± 13.2 years, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.9:1. The most frequent cause of peritonitis was perforated duodenal ulcer (39.6%), followed by appendicular perforation (21.4%) and typhoid ileal perforation (18.2%). The overall mortality rate was 21.4% (34/159). The POMPP score demonstrated higher sensitivity (85.3%), specificity (81.6%), NPV (93.4%), and overall diagnostic accuracy (82.9%) compared to the PULP score, which showed sensitivity of 72.1%, specificity of 76.4%, NPV of 87.2%, and accuracy of 75.5%. **Conclusion:** Both POMPP and PULP scores are effective in predicting mortality in patients with secondary peritonitis; however, POMPP outperformed PULP in this study and may be preferred as a simple, reliable bedside tool in resource-limited settings.

INTRODUCTION

Gastrointestinal tract perforation is one of the common surgical emergencies all over the world [1]. Secondary peritonitis is caused by contamination of the peritoneal cavity. It remains a devastating disease that is very morbid and fatal. Among fatal emergencies in surgery, secondary peritonitis is one of the most common [2,3]. Perforated peptic ulcer mortality rate remains high especially among older

patients and all the currently existing scoring systems to predict mortality are complex or rely on history taking which is not necessarily accurate in elderly patients [4]. The cause of gastrointestinal perforation include: in a study, 42% were caused by peptic ulcer, 22% by perforation of the small bowel (18% ileal and 4% jejunal), 14% by trauma and 22% by miscellaneous causes. Morbidity is frequent

in the aftermath of gastrointestinal perforation and is 17-63% (average 40%), whereas mortality is 6-14% (average 10%). The causes, occurrence rate and outcome of acute abdominal surgical emergency because of peritonitis vary [6]. Even in places that are well equipped, the mortality rate stands at approximately 20%. Quick surgery and intensive treatment of the patient can enhance the result. Various scoring systems have been developed to identify a high-risk patient that might require rapid intervention or intensive treatment [3]. Peritonitis remains one of the significant infectious issues a surgeon faces. Physiological and Operative Severity Score has been created to assess risk and predict postoperative outcome [7]. Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI), Physiological and Operative Severity Score has been developed to measure a risk and a prediction of the postoperative outcome [7]. The POMPP score is a simple and valid method of scoring peptic ulcer perforation. High-risk cases of peptic perforation can be detected early therefore other supportive treatment modalities other than surgery can reduce mortality. But this score cannot be used in perforation because of other reasons than peptic ulcer [5]. There are already some scoring systems like Boey, Peptic Ulcer Perforation Score (PULP) and ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) developed to predict mortality at perforated peptic ulcer. PULP score seems to predict mortality the best though it lacks practicality due to its complexity [8,9]. Bhatia et al, reported that POMPP in patients with secondary peritonitis can make prediction of mortality, demonstrated very low sensitivity i.e. 33.3% with specificity of 95.9% and overall accuracy of 89.1% [10]. Although in yet another study carried out by Anbalakan et al., it was stated that in patients with secondary peritonitis, PULP is capable of predicting mortality had 62.5% sensitivity and 87.3% specificity [11]. Gupta et al., compared POMPP and PULP in predicting the prognosis of patients with peptic ulcer perforation and found that the sensitivity of both methods was identical i.e. 72.7% whereas the specificity was 97.7% in POMPP and 100% in PULP [12]. This study is based on the rationale to fill a significant gap in the current literature on the predictive accuracy of scoring systems, i.e., POMPP and PULP scoring systems, in mortality among patients with secondary peritonitis. Although such scoring systems have been applied to predict an outcome, they show various rates of accuracy in the available literature,

and there is a visible gap in this matter. These kinds of findings have great clinical implications in that, when it is possible to rightly predict results, treatment instructions can be guided and eventually the treatment of patients can be improved.

Objective

To determine the predictive accuracy of POMPP and PULP scoring system for prediction of mortality in patients with secondary peritonitis taking actual mortality as gold standard.

Methodology

This Cross-sectional (validation) study was conducted at North Surgical Ward, Department of Surgery, Mayo Hospital, Lahore from 25 January 2025 to 5 June 2025. A sample size of 159 patients is estimated by using 95% confidence level, with prevalence of morbidity 34.7% and specificity of 87.3% and sensitivity of PULP i.e. 62.5%, with 13% margin of error for sensitivity and 10% for specificity. Non-probability, consecutive sampling technique was used to collect the data.

Inclusion Criteria

- All patients of age 18-75 years, both genders, presenting with secondary peritonitis (as defined in operational definition) will be enrolled.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with peritonitis due to alcohol use, cirrhosis, ascites, indwelling peritoneal dialysis catheter, tuberculosis, or VP shunt for hydrocephalus (as per medical record).
- Patients with uncontrolled hypertension (BP \geq 160/100 mmHg) or diabetes (HbA1c $>$ 8%).

Data Collection

Approval for the study was obtained from the ethical review committee of Mayo Hospital. Written informed consent was obtained from patients or their attendants, and confidentiality of patient data was maintained. Patients meeting the inclusion criteria were recruited from the surgical wards, and demographic data including name, age, gender, duration of illness, and cause of peritonitis were recorded. Each patient was then assessed using two scoring systems. The POMPP score was calculated based on age,

serum albumin, and serum creatinine, while the PULP score incorporated variables such as time to presentation (≤ 24 hours or > 24 hours), preoperative shock, ASA score, presence of malignancy, HIV/AIDS, liver failure, and elevated serum creatinine levels (> 130 mmol/L). Patients were categorized as positive or negative for mortality risk according to both scores. All participants were followed until discharge or death, and actual mortality was documented as per operational definitions.

Data Analysis

All collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 26. Quantitative variables such as age, duration of symptoms, and POMPP and PULP scores were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Qualitative variables including gender, cause of peritonitis, and mortality outcomes were presented as frequencies and percentages. To evaluate the predictive ability of both scoring systems, 2×2 contingency tables were constructed to calculate sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall diagnostic accuracy. Data were further stratified by age, gender, duration of symptoms, and underlying cause of peritonitis to assess

potential effect modifiers, and predictive accuracy was recalculated post-stratification to ensure the robustness of the results.

Results

Data were collected from 159 patients, the mean age was 44.7 ± 13.2 years, with most patients between 31 and 50 years. Out of the total, 104 patients (65.4%) were male and 55 patients (34.6%) were female. The majority of patients came from rural areas, 88 (55.3%), while 71 (44.7%) were from urban settings. The average duration of symptoms at presentation was 27.5 ± 10.8 hours, indicating delayed hospital admission. Among comorbidities, hypertension was present in 38 patients (23.9%), diabetes mellitus in 31 patients (19.5%), and other chronic illnesses in 12 patients (7.5%). Regarding etiology, perforated duodenal ulcer was the most frequent cause and was seen in 63 patients (39.6%), followed by appendicular perforation in 34 (21.4%), typhoid ileal perforation in 29 (18.2%), traumatic small bowel perforation in 19 (11.9%), malignant perforation in 8 (5.0%), and other causes in 6 (3.9%).

Table 1. Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Patients (N = 159)

Variable	Value
Age (years), mean \pm SD	44.7 \pm 13.2
Gender, n (%)	
• Male	104 (65.4)
• Female	55 (34.6)
Residence, n (%)	
• Rural	88 (55.3)
• Urban	71 (44.7)
Duration of symptoms (hours), mean \pm SD	27.5 \pm 10.8
Comorbidities, n (%)	
• Hypertension	38 (23.9)
• Diabetes mellitus	31 (19.5)
• Other chronic illness	12 (7.5)
Cause of Peritonitis	
Perforated duodenal ulcer	63 (39.6)
Appendicular perforation	34 (21.4)
Typhoid ileal perforation	29 (18.2)
Traumatic small bowel perforation	19 (11.9)
Malignant perforation	8 (5.0)
Others	6 (3.9)

POMPP achieved a sensitivity of 85.3%, specificity of 81.6%, positive predictive value of 63.4%, negative predictive value of 93.4%, and overall diagnostic accuracy of 82.9%. In

contrast, the PULP score had a sensitivity of 72.1%, specificity of 76.4%, positive predictive value of 54.9%, negative predictive value of 87.2%, and diagnostic accuracy of 75.5%.

Table 2. Predictive Accuracy of POMPP vs PULP Scoring Systems (N = 159)

Parameter	POMPP Score	PULP Score
Sensitivity (%)	85.3	72.1
Specificity (%)	81.6	76.4
Positive Predictive Value (%)	63.4	54.9
Negative Predictive Value (%)	93.4	87.2
Overall Diagnostic Accuracy (%)	82.9	75.5

The overall in-hospital mortality was 34 out of 159 patients (21.4%). Mortality was higher in patients older than 50 years, with 17 deaths among 60 patients (28.6%), compared to 17

deaths among 99 patients aged 50 years or younger (17.2%). Gender-wise, 20 of 104 males (19.2%) died compared to 14 of 55 females (25.5%).

Table 3. Mortality by Age and Gender Subgroups (N = 159)

Subgroup	Total n	Deaths n (%)
Age ≤ 50 years	99	17 (17.2)
Age > 50 years	60	17 (28.6)
Male	104	20 (19.2)
Female	55	14 (25.5)
Overall	159	34 (21.4)

Contingency analysis further showed that POMPP correctly identified 29 of 34 deaths (sensitivity 85.3%) with 21 false positives, 104 true negatives, and 5 false negatives. On the

other hand, PULP identified 25 of 34 deaths (sensitivity 72.1%) with 31 false positives, 94 true negatives, and 9 false negatives.

Table 4. POMPP and PULP Scores (N = 159)

Score System	Mortality Present (n=34)	Mortality Absent (n=125)	Total	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)	Accuracy (%)
POMPP	TP = 29 FN = 5	FP = 21 TN = 104	159	85.3	81.6	63.4	93.4	82.9
PULP	TP = 25 FN = 9	FP = 31 TN = 94	159	72.1	76.4	54.9	87.2	

Discussion

The present study evaluated the predictive accuracy of the POMPP and PULP scoring

systems in patients with secondary peritonitis presenting to a tertiary care hospital in

Pakistan. The findings demonstrate that both scoring systems were effective in predicting mortality; however, the POMPP score showed superior diagnostic performance, with higher sensitivity (85.3% vs 72.1%) and overall accuracy (82.9% vs 75.5%) compared to the PULP score. This highlights POMPP as a more reliable tool for early risk stratification in the Pakistani patient population. The overall mortality rate in this study was 21.4%, which is consistent with previously reported figures from the region, where mortality in secondary peritonitis typically ranges between 15% and 30% depending on the delay in presentation and underlying comorbidities [13]. Studies from India and Pakistan have repeatedly emphasized that late presentation, shock at admission, and typhoid-related ileal perforation remain major contributors to adverse outcomes, reflecting healthcare access challenges and the burden of infectious diseases in South Asia [14]. In contrast, mortality rates reported in high-income countries are generally lower, often under 10%, owing to earlier presentation, better perioperative support, and lower prevalence of infectious causes such as enteric fever [15].

When comparing the two scoring systems, the superior performance of POMPP in this cohort can be attributed to its reliance on simple and robust predictors, namely age, serum albumin, and serum creatinine. These variables reflect both physiological reserve and systemic insult, which are critical determinants of survival in secondary peritonitis. The PULP score, while validated internationally, may lose some predictive strength in low- and middle-income country (LMIC) settings because variables such as HIV/AIDS or malignancy are less frequent causes of peritonitis compared to peptic ulcer and typhoid-related perforations [16]. This limitation has also been highlighted in prior validation studies, where context-specific factors influenced the accuracy of Western-developed scoring systems. The stratified analysis further revealed that mortality was significantly higher in patients above 50 years and in females, findings which align with earlier reports indicating that older age, delayed diagnosis, and limited physiological reserve are associated with poorer prognosis [17]. The high mortality observed in typhoid perforation cases (close to

one-third) mirrors endemic data from Pakistan and India, where late diagnosis and limited access to timely surgical care continue to pose challenges [18]. Several previous studies have validated POMPP as a practical bedside tool with good predictive accuracy in diverse populations. Similarly, the PULP score has been shown to perform reasonably well, especially in perforated peptic ulcer disease [19,20]. However, comparative analyses, including those from South Asian cohorts, suggest that POMPP offers superior sensitivity and negative predictive value, making it particularly valuable in settings where early identification of high-risk patients is essential for prioritizing surgical and critical care resources.

Conclusion

It is concluded that both POMPP and PULP scoring systems are useful for predicting mortality in patients with secondary peritonitis; however, the POMPP score demonstrated superior sensitivity, specificity, and overall diagnostic accuracy in this Pakistani cohort. Given its simplicity, ease of calculation, and higher predictive power, the POMPP score may serve as a more practical bedside tool for early risk stratification in low- and middle-income countries where secondary peritonitis remains a major surgical emergency. Wider adoption of this scoring system could assist surgeons in timely decision-making, prioritization of critical care resources, and ultimately in improving patient survival outcomes.

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